

Deliverable 6.1

Project website

May 2024

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Project Information

Project full title:	Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem Ocean Observations
Project acronym:	BioEcoOcean
Grant agreement number:	101136748
Project start date and duration:	1st of February 2024, 48 months
Project website:	https://bioecoocean.org/
Project Coordinator:	Lina Mtwana Nordlund, Uppsala University

Deliverable information

Deliverable number:	6.1
Deliverable title:	Project website
Submission date:	31/05/2024
Level of dissemination:	Public
Work package and task:	WP6, Task 6.1
Lead Beneficiary:	IO PAN
Authors:	Artur Palacz (IO PAN), Dominik Krzyimiński (IO PAN), Nina Lepola, Lina Mtwana Nordlund
To be cited as:	Palacz, A., Krzyimiński, D., Lepola, N., Nordlund, L.K. 2024. Project website. BioEcoOcean deliverable 6.1. https://10.5281/zenodo.17786530

Executive Summary

This report provides a description of BioEcoOcean's project's public website (<https://bioecocean.eu/> and <https://bioecocean.org/>), its structure, purpose and functionality. The project website is an important dissemination tool, and it has been developed to serve as the primary online platform for dissemination and communication of project activities, results, and impacts. The website aims to increase visibility, engage stakeholders, and ensure the accessibility of information to the broader public and scientific community. The website is an informative platform presenting the main project information, such as the consortium structure, objectives of the project and work packages. D6.1 Project website report evaluates how the website meets the accessibility requirements and includes an overview of the plans for website evolution throughout the project time frame to meet the demands of successful communication, dissemination and exploitation of project results.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
IOC	The Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IO PAN	Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UU	Uppsala University
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

1. Introduction

The BioEcoOcean project's public website, accessible from two domains: <https://www.bioecocean.eu> and <https://bioecocean.org/>, serves as a crucial tool for disseminating and communicating key information about the project. It offers an effective platform for project stakeholders and the general public to gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges addressed by the project and the solutions proposed. This website, developed as the first deliverable under Work Package 6 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) was publicly launched on 31 May 2024. The website was designed jointly by IO PAN and Uppsala University, with additional input from consortium members. This report provides a brief description of the BioEcoOcean project's public website, covering its design, objectives, structure and functionality in Section 2, and considerations for its future developments in Section 3. Screenshots demonstrating examples of the website functionality are included in Appendix 1.

2. Website design, structure and functionality

2.1 Objectives and design

The project website was designed to fulfil its main objectives which are to:

- Provide comprehensive information about the BioEcoOcean project, including its objectives, methodologies and expected impacts.
- Disseminate project results and outputs to stakeholders, including policy-makers, researchers, industry professionals and the general public.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among project partners and stakeholders.
- Ensure transparency and accountability of project activities and progress.

To this end, the project website aimed to have a modern and user-friendly interface with an appealing visual identity by following the latest online standards in web development. The aim was to provide intuitive navigation within the website for all users across the project target audiences.

The website features a responsive design, ensuring accessibility across various devices, including desktops, tablets, and smartphones. Key features include:

- An intuitive navigation menu for easy access to different sections.
- Integration of social media links to enhance outreach and engagement.
- A news feed to keep visitors informed about the latest developments and events.

A more detailed website communication strategy will be described in the BioEcoOcean Initial Plan for

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication which will be submitted as Deliverable Report D6.2 in Month 6 of the project.

2.2. Domain name

The name of the project website domain was chosen to ensure it is immediately recognizable and easily findable for the broad user pool which the project aims to address via its website. The website is accessible from two parallel domains: <https://bioecoocean.eu> and <https://bioecoocean.org>. The latter domain will help recognize the project's ambition and active engagement with the global ocean observing community and associated stakeholders. It was also selected with the perspective of enabling long-term legacy and website maintenance after the project officially ends, in particular considering the long-term promotion and application of the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science and associated online resources which will be primarily accessed through the project website.

2.3. Website structure and functionality

The website is structured to include the following sections:

- **Home:** Overview of the project, latest news, and highlights
- **About:** Detailed information about the project, its goals, and methodologies
 - **Objectives:** Description of project overall aims
 - **Work Packages:** Description of work packages and their specific objectives and activities
 - **Partners:** Profiles of project partner institutions and their roles, member profiles (integrated with IOC-UNESCO's OceanExpert platform)
- **Actions:** Description of key project actions organized by three types of living labs:
 - **Blueprint Living Lab:** Information about development of the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science
 - **Focal Living Labs:** Description of project research focused on Biology & Ecosystems Essential Ocean Variables
 - **Learning Living Lab:** Capacity development resources
- **Outputs:** Publications, reports, data, presentations and other outputs generated by the project; fully integrated with the BioEcoOcean Community on the Zenodo.org where all project outputs are being deposited and made accessible during and beyond the lifetime of the project
- **Resources:** Additional project materials (e.g. project logo, fact sheets, videos)

- **News & Events:** Updates on project progress and related news. Information on upcoming events, workshops, and conference
- **Contact:** Contact details of Project Coordination and Project Communication for further inquiries

In addition, the top menu bar also provides direct access to BioEcoOcean’s social media channels, and two additional items:

- **Get Involved:** Invitation to take part in surveys or other means of active participation in the project for collaborators and other stakeholders from outside of the consortium
- **Webinars:** Providing direct links to project’s webinars

2.4. Website accessibility requirements

The website has been designed to comply with international standards for accessible web content, specifically the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0. These guidelines encompass a broad spectrum of recommendations aimed at enhancing the accessibility of web content to individuals with various disabilities, including but not limited to blindness and low vision, deafness and hearing loss, learning disabilities, cognitive limitations, limited movement, speech disabilities, photosensitivity, and combinations of these.

In order to enhance the accessibility of the BioEcoOcean website, a dedicated function has been incorporated to enable users to adjust text size, modify contrast settings to a darker mode, and underline links (Figure 1.)

Figure 1: Accessibility options available on the BioEcoOcean website.

The website's accessibility was assessed using the WAVE web accessibility evaluation tool developed by WebAIM.org (<https://wave.webaim.org/>). This tool provides visual feedback on the accessibility of web content, aligning errors with WCAG 2.2 failures. Additionally, the WAVE interface facilitates human evaluation of numerous other aspects of accessibility and compliance with Web Content Accessibility Guidelines and Section 508. The results of this evaluation are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: BioEcoOcean website accessibility evaluation using the WAVE tool.

3. Future developments

The website remains open to further changes and addition of modes and functions depending on the need. Plans for future enhancements include but are not limited to:

- Subscription form for project newsletter
- Blueprint development platform and associated resources integrated into the project website
- Addition of multimedia content, including videos and webinar recordings
- Regular updates to the project results and publications section as new data becomes available

Appendices

Appendix 1. Snapshots from the website

Screenshots from the Home page:

Screenshot from the About page:

Screenshots from Outputs page:

Partners

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement number 101136748. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.